

Optofluidic modulation of Polarization Active Planar Bragg Microcavities

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Bragg microcavities (BMs) formed by the successive stacking of nanocolumnar porous SiO₂ and TiO₂ layers with slanted, zig-zag, chiral and vertical configurations are prepared by physical vapor deposition at oblique angles (PV-OAD) while azimuthally varying the substrate orientation during the multilayer growth. The slanted and zig-zag BMs act as wavelength selective optical retarders when they are illuminated with linearly polarized light, while no polarization dependence is observed for the chiral and vertical cavities. This distinct optical behavior is attributed to a fence-bundling association of nanocolumns as observed by FIB-SEM in the slanted and zig-zag microcavities. The outstanding retarder response of the optically active BMs can be effectively modulated by dynamic pore infiltration with liquids of different refraction indices acting as a switch of the polarization behaviour. The unprecedented polarization and tunable optofluidic properties of these layered photonic systems have been successfully simulated with a simple model that assumes a certain birefringence for the individual stacked layers and accounts for the light interference phenomena developed in the BMs. The possibilities of this type of optically active BMs for liquid sensing and monitoring applications are discussed.

1. Introduction

The last innovations in the field of optofluidics have led to the development of highly versatile optical systems with a wide range of applications both at the micro and macroscales and a high impact in fields such as energy^[1], photonics^[2], microfluidics^[3] or sensors and biosensors^[4]. Outstanding examples relying on the light control by means of liquids flowing through devices include adaptive and tuneable microlenses^[5,6], optofluidic dye laser^[7] or advanced optofluidic microscopes^[8]. Light polarization by liquids containing chiral molecules or by anisotropic solids is a classical optical principle widely used in advanced technologies for chemical analysis, communications, displays and photonics that, except for very recent works using complex polymer particles^[9], has not been addressed within optofluidic schemes aiming at merging optics and microfluidics in a device^[3]. In the present work we report that light polarization can be effectively controlled by liquid circulation through a new type of polarization active planar Bragg microcavities (BM) devices prepared by physical vapour oblique angle deposition (PV-OAD). This liquid-mediated control of the activity of planar BMs constitutes a first case of polarizer thin films optofluidics with high impact prospects for the fabrication of polarization active systems, wavelength retarders, photonic sensors or liquid monitoring devices.

Thin films fabrication by PV-OAD, also known as Glancing Angle Deposition (GLAD)^[10,11], is a straightforward procedure to tailor film porosities while achieving a strict control over optical properties such as refraction index^[12,13] or optical anisotropy and birefringence^[14,15]. In the called “sculptured thin films”^[16,17], a class of nanostructured GLAD materials, their singular topography, geometry and in-depth architecture permits an effective control of their refractive index and birefringence and the development of optically active photonic structures^[18–23] or helicoidally bi-anisotropic media acting for example as narrow band pass optical filters^[24], selective circularly polarized light transmitters^[25] or selective linearly polarized transmitters^[26]. On the other hand, although polarization inactive SiO₂-TiO₂ one

dimensional photonic crystals (1DPC)^[27,28] and Bragg microcavities (BM)^[29] have been also prepared by PVD-OAD, no polarization activity is known for such two-oxide layered systems. Herein, we demonstrate for the first time that two-oxide BMs prepared by PVD-OAD can be manufactured as polarization active systems behaving as wavelength dependent retarders. We also show that this polarization activity can be systematically and continuously controlled adjusting the refractive index of the liquids circulating through these porous layer structures. To complete the study, other important parts of this research aim at unravelling the nanostructural features responsible for the polarization activity of these porous BM and at simulating their striking polarization behaviour. For this purpose, we have developed a simple optical model where each particular layer in the stack is taken as birefringent in a degree that varies with the refraction index of the liquid filling the pores.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Morphology and bundling association

To determine the nanostructural factors responsible for the polarization activity of the PV-OAD BMs, we have prepared and characterized four types of TiO₂-SiO₂ microcavities depicting different nanocolumn arrangements: i) *slanted*, prepared at constant azimuthal orientation of the substrate during deposition of successive layers; ii) *zig-zag* and iii) *chiral* obtained turning the substrate, respectively, by 180° and 90° for each layer of the stack; iv) *vertical*, deposited while continuously rotating the substrate around its azimuth. Surprisingly, the two first BMs present a strong polarization activity when interrogated with linearly polarized light, while the two latter are practically insensitive to the polarization. Thanks to a thorough analysis by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and a field ion beam (FIB) set-up we have been able to show that association of nanocolumns, a rather general phenomenon in

OAD films known with the term *bundling*^[30,31], is the critical morphological feature responsible for the singular behaviour of the *slanted* and *zig-zag* BMs.

Figure 1 displays a series of cross section and normal micrographs taken for the TiO₂/SiO₂ BMs deposited on a silicon wafer. The cross section images and schemes in this figure show the characteristic nanocolumnar microstructure of the *slanted* (i), *zig-zag* (ii), *vertical* (iii) and *chiral* (iv) multilayer systems (the supporting information **Scheme S1** illustrate the different nanostructural arrangements with a dynamic 360°-view scheme of the different microstructures). The normal images of the *slanted* and *zig-zag* and, to a minor extent, the *chiral* BMs also reveal a preferential arrangement of material along the direction perpendicular to the vapour flux, an anisotropy which is further supported by the 2-fold symmetry of their Fourier transforms (FT) reported in the figure. Meanwhile, the highly symmetric FT shape of the *vertical* BMs clearly reflects an uncorrelated distribution of column terminations at the surface of this sample.

Bundling association of nanocolumns is believed to extend along the whole thickness of single oxide OAD thin films^[30–33], a feature that we confirmed by FIB-SEM analysis of the BMs. **Figure 2** shows a series of cross section micrographs along the π (perpendicular to the film surface in a direction parallel to the *bundling*), Δ (perpendicular to the film surface in a direction perpendicular to the *bundling*), and Ω planes (close to the perpendicular to the nanocolumns direction) defined in the scheme of the *slanted* microstructure included in this figure. The layered distribution of brightness observed in the Back Scatter Electron (BSE) micrographs reflects the different atomic numbers of the SiO₂ and TiO₂ layers. In addition, the π -plane micrographs (i.e., panels (a) and (b)) of the *slanted* BM show that nanocolumns associate along the whole film thickness, i.e., association is not restricted to a single layer of the stack. We will call this nanocolumn association extending from one material layer to the next as *fence-bundling*, a specific microstructural feature that has not been previously reported in the literature. In the Δ -plane image (i.e., panel c), it is also apparent that large mesopores

extends through the whole material and that no disruption of nanocolumns morphology occurs when passing from one layer (e.g., TiO₂) to the next (e.g., SiO₂). Finally, the image taken along the Ω -plane (i.e., panel d) confirms that both mesopores and nanocolumns arrange linearly along the surface bundling direction. Similarly, images taken along the π and Δ planes for the *zig-zag* microstructure (panels (e) and (f)) show the development of equivalent *fence-bundling* association extending through the whole BM. Lack of *fence-bundling* association in the *vertical* BM and only a negligible association in the individual layers in the *chiral* BM (i.e., panels g) and f) and **Figure S2**) are clear differences with respect to the two other photonic structures. The direct assessment of the topography evolution during ion etching of the *slanted* BMs reported as a video of SEM images, **Video S3**, confirms that this *fence-bundling* association extends through the whole BM thickness and that no boundary effects exists between stacked layers.

2.2 Polarization activity of planar BMs

The *fence-bundling* arrangement of nanocolumns in the *slanted* and *zig-zag* BMs has direct effects on the optical properties of these structures when examined with linearly polarized light. **Figure 3** shows a series of optical transmittance spectra recorded around the resonant peak for the four studied BMs using linearly polarized light oriented with its polarization plane parallel (i.e. $\varphi=0^\circ$) or perpendicular (i.e. $\varphi=90^\circ$) to the surface *bundling* direction. Unlike the spectra of the *vertical* and *chiral* BMs which are almost unaffected by the orientation of polarized light, the *slanted* and *zig-zag* BMs develop two different resonant peaks for φ equal to 0° and 90° , a double peak structure for other orientations and an almost equivalent intensity of the two peaks when $\varphi=45^\circ$. The separation between the two resonant peaks is 18 nm (*slanted*) and 23 nm (*zig-zag*). The positions and Q factors of the resonant peaks summarized in **Table 1** are practically identical for the two polarizations in the *vertical*

BM, but strongly differ for the *titled* and *zig-zag* structures and present slight changes for the *chiral* BM.

The optical behaviour depicted in Figure 3 can be simulated with an optical interference model where the SiO₂ or TiO₂ stacked layers of the BM are birefringent. For the *slanted*, *zig-zag* and *chiral* structures, the negative uniaxial anisotropy associated to each individual layer can be described by a fast optical axis (low refractive index) along a surface direction perpendicular to the *fence-bundling* (n_p) and a slow axis (high refractive index) along the *fence-bundling* direction at the surface plane (n_b). **Figure 4** demonstrates that this simple model properly reproduces the transmittance spectra of the *zig-zag* BMs upon continuous φ rotation. This angular dependence supports the use of this BM to determine the orientation of the polarization plane of light. The birefringence (i.e. $\Delta n = n_p - n_b$) of the individual layers introduced in the model to properly reproduce the optical behaviour of the *zig-zag* BM amounts to $\Delta n = -0.150$ and -0.043 for TiO₂ and SiO₂ layers, respectively. From a structural point of view, this optical anisotropy stands for a difference in void fraction of $\sim 20\%$ between the more compact *fence-bundling* direction and the perpendicular to it. A similar analysis for the *slanted* structure, **Figure S4**, confirms the validity of this optical model to simulate the polarization response of the polarization active BMs.

2.3 BM thin films as wave retarders

Zig-zag and *slanted* BMs behave as optical retarders or wave-plates^[34] and are characterized by resolving a linearly polarised beam into two orthogonal components separated by a wavelength dependent phase shift. **Figure 5** shows a scheme of the polarization state of light (Figure 5a) and the transmittance spectra recorded through the *zig-zag* BM placed between two polarizers either in crossed (Figure 5b) or aligned (Figure 5d) configurations. The function of the first polarizer is to generate linearly polarized light, while the transmitted spectra in the figure are recorded as a function of the angles φ_1 , φ_2 formed by the bundling

direction of sample and the first and second polarizer planes, respectively. Selected results of similar experiments conducted with the *slanted*, *vertical* and *chiral* BMs show that, as expected, only the former presents similar retarder behaviour (see **Figure S5**).

It is apparent in Figure 5 that for the cross-polarizer configuration and the BM bundling direction aligned along the polarization plane of light (i.e. $\varphi_1=90^\circ$ and $\varphi_2=0^\circ$) (Figure 5b), no light passes through the system. Meanwhile, progressively more intense spectra are recorded when azimuthally rotating the BM (i.e., $\varphi_1<90^\circ$ and $\varphi_2=90^\circ-\varphi_1$) up to reach a maximum intensity for $\varphi_1=\varphi_2=45^\circ$, an optical behaviour that could be successfully reproduced by simulation (c.f. Figure 5c). When the BM is placed between two aligned polarizers at $\varphi_1=\varphi_2=0^\circ$ (see Figure 5d and simulated spectra in Figure 5e), the transmittance spectrum results identical to that recorded in the absence of the second polarizer (i.e., identical to that reported in Figure 4 for $\varphi=0^\circ$). The transmittance spectra drastically changes for other azimuthal orientations of the sample with respect to the aligned polarizers (i.e., for $\varphi_1=\varphi_2\neq 0^\circ$), indicating that the BM modifies the polarization state of light. Thus, for $\varphi_1=\varphi_2>0^\circ$, there is a progressive transfer of intensity from the high to the short wavelength resonant peak. Then, these two peaks depict a similar intensity for $\varphi_1=\varphi_2=45^\circ$, experience a reversal in intensity ratio for $\varphi_1=\varphi_2>45^\circ$ and finally reach a maximum intensity/complete neglect at $\varphi_1=\varphi_2=90^\circ$.

The pure retarder behaviour of the BM is confirmed verifying that the sum of the crossed and parallel polarizers spectra in Figure 5 matches the spectra in Figure 4 obtained with linear polarized light (see Figure S5). Further insights in this polarization behaviour, in particular into the light ellipticity as a function of wavelength and azimuthal orientation of sample, could be retrieved calculating the intensity ratio between signals measured with cross and parallel polarizers. Selected wavelength dependences of this ellipticity are reported in **Figure S6**, being worth noting that when equivalent transmitted intensities are measured for the cross and parallel configurations, the BM acts as a perfect quarter-wave plate^[34].

The singular wavelength retarder behaviour of the optically active BMs evidenced in Figures 5 and S5 stems from interferences within the multilayer structure, whereby each layer behaves as an individual retarder inducing a retardance $\delta = \Delta n * t/\lambda$, where t is the thickness of the birefringent medium (i.e., layer thickness), λ the wavelength of light and Δn the difference between extraordinary and the ordinary refractive indices of the layer, $\Delta n = n_p - n_o$.

Despite the quite different arrangement of nanocolumns in the *zig-zag* and *slanted* BMs, their equivalent retarder behaviour (see Figure 5a and Figure S5) points to that the *fence-bundling* association of nanocolumns is the common microstructural feature inducing the single layer birefringence responsible for the wave retarder response of the whole device. The lack of *fence-bundling* association in the *vertical* BMs discards such a single-layer birefringence and consequently prevents any wave retarder function for the whole structure (see Figure 5a and Figure S5 b and c). For the *chiral* BM, besides the limited *fence-bundling* association observed in its microstructure (c.f., Figure 2 f)), the 90° change in the tilting orientation of nanocolumns in successive layers precludes a common reference orientation for the slow and fast optical axis in different layers and, therefore, any significant polarization activity for the whole device.

2.4 Optofluidic behaviour of polarization active BMs

An outstanding characteristic of PV-OAD single or stacked multilayer photonic crystals or BMs, is their high porosity and the possibility that their optical response can be altered by liquid infiltration^[28,29]. In previous studies on the liquid infiltration of 1DPC and *chiral* BMs (i.e., polarization inactive) we found a pore fraction of ca. 50% that were filled with liquids in its practical totality. A similar value is expected for the BMs studied here. **Figure 6** shows a series of transmittance spectra recorded for the polarization active *zig-zag* BM successively infiltrated with water (n: 1.333), ethanol (n: 1.362) and toluene (n: 1.496). It is apparent that, besides a shift in the resonant peak positions, the magnitude of wavelength splitting between the resonant peaks recorded with unpolarized light decreases from 23 nm in the originally

empty *zig-zag* device to 8, 7 and 5 nm, when infiltrated with these liquids. The well-matched simulated spectra in **Figure S8** sustains that filling the pores of the structure with these liquids produces a decrease in the birefringence of the individual layers from $\Delta n_{TiO_2} = -0.150$ and $\Delta n_{SiO_2} = -0.043$ when the BM is empty (i.e., filled with air) to $\Delta n_{TiO_2} = -0.112$ and $\Delta n_{SiO_2} = -0.011$ (water); $\Delta n_{TiO_2} = -0.109$ and $\Delta n_{SiO_2} = -0.009$ (ethanol); or $\Delta n_{TiO_2} = -0.094$ and $\Delta n_{SiO_2} = 0.004$ (toluene).

Furthermore, it is possible to verify that the *retarder* function of the active BMs can be modulated by liquid infiltration. Thus, although liquid infiltration attenuates the optical activity of the BMs (see **Video S9**), this is accompanied by changes in shape and intensity of the resonant peaks which constitute the basis of the outstanding optofluidic effects of these devices. **Figure 7** shows the spectra recorded with the cross and parallel polarizers configurations and a $\varphi_1=\varphi_2=45^\circ$ azimuthal orientation of the *zig-zag* BM filled with air (taken as a reference), water, ethanol and toluene. As expected, increasing the refractive index of the liquid produces a shift to longer wavelengths in the position of the resonant peaks. In addition, their intensities increase/decrease for the cross and parallel configurations as the refraction index of the infiltration liquid increases. An outstanding result of this experiment is that, after calibration, the intensity ratio between the two resonant peaks is a direct measurement of the refraction index of the infiltration liquid. The potential of this behaviour for analytical applications with solutions (the refraction index directly correlates with solute concentrations) is quite obvious particularly because, even if the actual two resonant peak intensities would be proportional to the excitation beam flux, their ratio would be independent of malfunctions or time instabilities of the light source.

2.5.- Polarization activity and fence-bundling association

From a microstructural point of view, the reported optofluidic response of the polarization active *zig-zag* and *slanted* BMs depends on the development of a *fence-bundling* association

between nanocolumns. Bundling association in PV-OAD thin films has been known since the earliest investigations with this deposition procedure^[30,31], although this microstructural feature has been scarcely used for the development of optical devices^[32,33].

2. Conclusion

The present study constitutes a first example of the interplay between microstructure, light polarization and liquid-controlled properties of OAD layered materials that should serve to develop new applications in fields like sensing, optical device manufacturing and optofluidics. We have demonstrated that the *fence-bundling* association of nanocolumns in multilayer thin films deposited by evaporation at oblique angles can be engineered to develop polarization active BMs acting as wavelength retarders. Filling the highly porous structure of these multilayers with liquids attenuates the optical activity (see Video S9) and gives rise to quite striking optofluidic responses easily monitored by the position, shape and intensity of the resonant peak(s). In particular, we have shown that the liquid modulation of the retarder function of the BM can be used to detect the orientation of polarization plane of light or for the analysis of liquids when integrated in microfluidic devices. Taking into account the easy manufacturing procedure of these multilayer structures, its compatibility with any kind of substrates and the possibility of using masks, we anticipate a wide range of optofluidic applications for this type of planar BM systems.

4. Experimental Section

Fabrication of BMs and optofluidic devices.

Uniform, mechanically stable, and highly porous BMs made of alternated layers of TiO₂ and SiO₂ have been prepared by oblique angle deposition (OAD) according to the procedure reported for single layer deposition^[35]. The investigated porous BMs were e-beam evaporated on glass plates of 1.2 × 2.5 cm² at a zenithal angle of 70° (α). For electron microscopy

characterization, samples were simultaneously deposited on a silicon wafer. Other experimental details can be found in this previous work. The BMs consisted of 2×7 individual layers with a thickness of approximately 85 nm, plus one SiO₂ middle layer of approximately 200 nm thickness. Four different types of BMs have been prepared depicting *slanted* (i), *zig-zag* (ii), *chiral* (iii) or *vertical* (iv) microstructures. These different morphologies were obtained by keeping fix the substrate for the *slanted* BM or by azimuthally turning the substrate from one layer to the next in the *zig-zag* (180°) and *chiral* (90°) and continuously (40 rpm) in the *vertical* configuration.

For the optofluidic essays the BMs deposited on a glass plate were sandwiched with another glass plate as reported previously^[29]. This simple microfluidic arrangement enabled handling the device as a plate substrate in front of the light beam of a spectrometer and to record spectra while replacing the circulating liquid by simple injection.

Characterization of BMs

Cross section and normal scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images were obtained in a Hitachi S4800 field emission microscope for samples deposited on a silicon wafer that were cleaved for cross-section analysis.

FIB-SEM analysis was performed using a FEI Helios Nanolab 660 tool. First, SEM images were acquired normal to the surface at 2keV primary beam energy using both Secondary Electrons (SE) for topographic and Back Scatter Electrons (BSE) for compositional information. Thereafter, an optional strip of Pt was deposited using electron beam and ion beam induced deposition in order to prevent ion damage to the surface. Subsequently 2 trenches were milled at 30keV Ga⁺ ion energy at 90° angle with one another and oriented parallel and orthogonal to the preference direction seen in the SEM images from the surface. After coarse milling, the side surfaces were polished using a 30keV, 80pA Ga⁺ ion beam. The cuts were then observed with the electron beam under 52° incidence in the same modes (SE and BSE) as mentioned before. In Figure 2 (b, c, d) the BSE images show a periodic contrast

that we attribute to the different atomic numbers of the stacked TiO₂ (bright) and SiO₂ (dark) layers and other possible morphological effects.

UV–vis transmission spectra were recorded in normal incidence with a Cary 100 instrument. In order to analyse the optical activity with polarized light, a linear polarizer was placed before the sample. A second polarizer crossed or aligned with respect the first one was placed after the sample to assess the retarder behaviour of the BMs and optofluidic devices upon azimuthal rotation.

Simulation of the optical response and polarization dependence

Simulation of the optical response of the optofluidic device was done using WVASE32 software [J. A. Woollan Co.] applied to a Bragg microcavity consisting of two Bragg reflectors separated by a “defect layer”. Each Bragg reflector has 7 layers, with a HLHLHLH structure, where H denotes high index material (i.e., TiO₂) and L low index material (i.e., SiO₂). The defect layer was a L material. The optical model relies on the assumption of a birefringent behaviour of the stacked SiO₂ or TiO₂ individual layers in the *slanted*, *zig-zag* and, partially, *chiral* microstructures. The negative uniaxial anisotropic medium in each layer of the *slanted* and *zig-zag* BMs has been characterized by a fast optical axis (low refractive index, n_p) in the direction perpendicular to the *fence-bundling* association and a slow axis (high refractive index, n_b) in the *fence-bundling* plane. For the *chiral* BM, each layer was taken as a positive uniaxial material, with an optical axis normal to the layer, along the nanocolumn direction.

The model interpreted the birefringence $\Delta n = n_p - n_b$ as resulting from the difference in porosity along the–bundling direction and the perpendicular to it on the surface plane. The effect of porosity on the optical behaviour was simulated according to Maxwell–Garnett effective medium approximation to describe a composite material formed by a compact media (i.e., either compact TiO₂ or SiO₂) mixed with voids filled with either air or liquids with different refraction indices. For these calculations, it is assumed that both materials H and L

have the same percentage of pore volume and the refractive index of the individual layers was described by a typical Cauchy wavelength dispersion.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the author and below.

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Figure 1. Microstructure of planar BMs. FIB-SEM cross section images of the BMs and scheme for a slanted structure showing the cross section planes used for the analysis and the resulting lateral surfaces in each case. a) to d) BSE images for the *slanted* BMs along the different analysis planes: a) micrograph taken for a cross section along plane π ; b) the same as A in an enlarged scale; c) micrograph taken for a cross section along plane Δ ; d) micrograph taken for a cross section along plane Ω . The enlarged image at the right of micrographs a) is taken in SE mode to better visualize the lateral surface generated by the ion erosion. e) and f) BSE cross section micrographs taken for the *zig-zag* microstructure along planes π and Δ

respectively. g) BSE cross section micrograph taken for the *vertical* BM along plane Δ . h) Ditto for a *chiral* BM.

Figure 2. FIB-SEM cross section images of the BMs and scheme for a slanted structure showing the cross section planes used for the analysis and the resulting lateral surfaces in each case. a) to d) BSE images for the *slanted* BMs along the different analysis planes: a) micrograph taken for a cross section along plane π ; b) the same as A in an enlarged scale; c) micrograph taken for a cross section along plane Δ ; d) micrograph taken for a cross section along plane Ω . The enlarged image at the right of micrographs a) is taken in SE mode to

better visualize the lateral surface generated by the ion erosion. e) and f) BSE cross section micrographs taken for the *zig-zag* microstructure along planes π and Δ respectively. g) BSE cross section micrograph taken for the *vertical* BM along plane Δ . h) Ditto for a *chiral* BM.

Figure 3. Transmission spectra recorded around the resonant peak for the indicated BMs with linearly polarized light oriented at 0° , 45° and 90° with respect to the perpendicular to the arrival flux direction.

Figure 4. Polarization angle dependence. Experimental a) and simulated b) spectra around the resonant peak of a *zig-zag* BM when recorded with linearly polarized light at the indicated angles formed between the polarization plane and the *bundling* direction (i.e., azimuthally rotating the sample by the indicated angles).

Figure 5. Polarization angle dependence through a second polarizer. (a) Scheme of the two polarizers set up and light polarization behaviour with the polarization active BM placed in-between and perpendicular to the direction of light. This particular representation corresponds to the cross polarizer configuration. b, c) Evolution of experimental (b) and simulated (c) spectra around the resonant peak of a *zig-zag* BM when recorded through two cross polarizers by azimuthally rotating the BM as indicated. e) Evolution of experimental (d) and simulated (e) spectra of the resonant peak of a *zig-zag* BM when recorded through two parallel polarizers by azimuthally rotating the BM as indicated.

Figure 6. Optofluidic modulation of polarization behaviour. Experimental spectra for a *zigzag* BM recorded with unpolarised and 0° and 90° linearly polarized light for the as-prepared (i.e. air filled) (a) and water (b), ethanol (c) and toluene (d) infiltrated structure.

Figure 7.-Optofluidic modulation of polarization behavior. Transmittance spectra recorded through the *zig-zag* BM azimuthally oriented 45° with respect to the two polarisers either in cross (x) or parallel (II) configurations. Bottom) Spectra recorded for the BM pores filled with air. Top) Spectra recorded for the BM pores filled with liquids of different refractive indices as indicated.

Table 1. Resonant peaks positions and Q factors of the different Bragg Microcavities

	$\phi(^{\circ})$	<i>Slanted</i>	<i>Zig-zag</i>	<i>Vertical</i>	<i>Chiral</i>
Position (nm)	0	619.8	614.6	702.5	603.9
	90	601.9	591.6	702.7	602.2
Q factor	0	31.9	31.9	19.9	30.5
	90	26.5	28.4	19.7	26.8

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TiO₂-SiO₂ multilayers prepared by oblique angle deposition in a slanted and zig-zag configuration present a *fence-bundling* association of nanocolumns that confer them an outstanding optical retarder behavior when illuminated with linearly polarized light. The modulation of this response by infiltrating their porous structure with liquids of different refraction indices can be used for sensing and monitoring applications.

Keyword. Optically active multilayer film, OAD, GLAD, wavelength retarder, optofluidic, light polarization

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Title: Optofluidic modulation of Polarization Active Planar Bragg Microcavities

ToC figure

Supporting Information

Optofluidic modulation of Polarization Active Planar Bragg Microcavities

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Scheme S1 (dynamic).- Nanostructural arrangement of nanocolumns of the different architectures investigated in this work as illustrated with a 360°-view dynamic scheme.

Figure S2.- Enlarge SE micrograph of a vertical BM to show the lack of fence-bundling association. A sketch is including clarifying the FIB-SEM analysis.

Video S3.- Video showing the evolution of the images taken from the surface of a slanted BM by FIB-SEM during the ion milling.

Figure S4.- Experimental a) and simulated b) spectra around the resonant peak of a *slanted* BM when recorded with linearly polarized light at the indicated angles formed between the polarization plane and the *bundling* direction (i.e., azimuthally rotating the sample by the indicated angles).

Figure S5.- Experimental (left) and simulated (right) evolution of spectra and spectra for *slanted* (a), *vertical* (b) and *chiral* (c) BMs when recorded with two cross polarizers and the indicated azimuthal orientation of the sample according to the scheme of figure 5 in the main text.

Figure S6.- Representation of the sum of the transmission spectra recorded with the parallel (II) and crossed (x) configurations and the indicated azimuthal orientations of the *zig-zag* BM.

Figure S7.- Degree of ellipticity of light determined as the indicated intensity ratios between the transmission spectra recorded for the *zig-zag* BM with parallel (II) and cross (x) polarizer configurations and 0° , 15° , 30° and 45° of azimuthal orientation. At the wavelengths at which the two lines interfere for $\phi_1=30^\circ$ and 45° the light is circularly polarized (gray circles in the figure).

Figure S8.- Simulated spectra for a *zig-zag* BM recorded with unpolarised and 0° and 90° linearly polarized light for the as-prepared (i.e. air filled) (a) and water (b), ethanol (c) and toluene (d) infiltrated structure.

Figure S9.- Video illustrating the attenuation of optical activity by infiltrating the BMs with a liquid